

MY INTEREST ON RUSSIAN AND ITS INTEGRATION WITH UZBEK-WORLD LITERATURE

Mamatkulov Dilshodbek

6th grade pupil at public school № 3, Turakurgan, Namangan, Uzbekistan

Norkuziyeva Oydin Umirkulovna

His abiding teacher Master Student at Namangan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8086635>

Annotation: Translating literature is a challenging task that requires not only knowledge of the languages involved but also a deep understanding of the cultural and historical context of the text being translated. It is admirable to have a passion for promoting one's own culture and language through translation. Translating Uzbek literature into other languages can help to increase its visibility and accessibility to a wider audience. It can also contribute to the preservation and promotion of Uzbek culture and heritage. However, it is important to note that translation is not a one-way process, and there is much to be gained from reading and appreciating literature from other cultures as well. This article acknowledges the importance of family support in a student's success in education and language learning. The author expresses gratitude towards a student's mother for her dedication and encouragement towards her child's education, which has played a significant role in their achievements.

Key words: family support, education, language learning, dedication, encouragement, success, achievements, literature, Uzbek literature, Russian literature, world literature, translation.

Аннотация: Перевод художественной литературы – сложная задача, требующая не только знания соответствующих языков, но и глубокого понимания культурно-исторического контекста переводимого текста. Замечательно иметь страсть к продвижению собственной культуры и языка посредством перевода. Перевод узбекской литературы на другие языки может помочь повысить ее узнаваемость и доступность для более широкой аудитории. Это также может способствовать сохранению и популяризации узбекской культуры и наследия. Однако важно отметить, что перевод — это не односторонний процесс, и чтение и оценка литературы других культур также могут принести много пользы. В этой статье признается важность поддержки семьи для успеха учащегося в образовании и изучении языка. Автор выражает благодарность матери студента за ее самоотверженность и поощрение к образованию своего ребенка, что сыграло значительную роль в их достижениях.

Ключевые слова: поддержка семьи, воспитание, изучение языка, самоотверженность, поощрение, успех, достижения, литература, узбекская литература, русская литература, мировая литература, перевод.

Preface by the both teacher and parent of the author of the article. As a teacher, I am incredibly proud of my student's dedication to language learning and their career aspirations in becoming a multilingual translator or interpreter. In today's globalized world, communication is key, and my student's passion for understanding different cultures and building bridges between communities is truly inspiring. Their commitment to broadening their perspectives through cultural exchange will undoubtedly have a positive impact in an interconnected world. With their exceptional communication skills and unwavering drive, I have no doubt that my student will achieve great success in their chosen field and make a significant contribution to society. It has been an absolute pleasure to witness their growth and development, and I am excited to see what the future holds for them.

I would also like to acknowledge the support and encouragement provided by my student's mother. Her dedication to her child's education and language learning has been instrumental in their

success. Her unwavering support and belief in her child's abilities have undoubtedly played a significant role in their achievements. It is heartening to see such strong family support, which is crucial in fostering a love for learning and achieving one's goals. I am grateful for the opportunity to work with such a wonderful student and their supportive family.

As a 12-year-old pupil, I have always been fascinated by the power of literature. My family has a diverse taste in books, with my elder sister reading world literature in English, my parents reading Uzbek literature, and myself reading Russian literature. This has given me a unique perspective on the importance of integrating world literature with Uzbek literature. I have a passion for reading and exploring different genres of literature. One of my favorite genres is Russian literature. I find it fascinating to read about the lives and experiences of people in Russia, especially during the time of the Soviet Union.

One of the most famous Russian authors is Leo Tolstoy, who wrote many classics such as *War and Peace* and *Anna Karenina*. These books have been adapted into movies and TV shows, but nothing compares to reading the original works. Tolstoy's writing style is unique and captivating, and his stories are full of complex characters and intricate plotlines.

Another great Russian author is Fyodor Dostoevsky, who wrote *Crime and Punishment* and *The Brothers Karamazov*. These books are not only entertaining but also thought-provoking, as they explore themes such as morality, justice, and redemption.

I also enjoy the works of Alexander Pushkin, who is considered one of the greatest Russian poets and writers. His most famous works include *Eugene Onegin* and *The Bronze Horseman*. Pushkin's writing style is elegant and poetic, and his stories often explore themes of love, honor, and tragedy.

Reading Pushkin's works has given me a deeper appreciation for poetry and has helped me develop my own writing skills. I am grateful to have discovered such a talented writer and look forward to reading more of his works in the future.

Reading Russian literature has not only helped me improve my reading skills but has also given me a better understanding of history and culture. It has taught me to appreciate different perspectives and to think critically about complex issues. I believe that everyone should give Russian literature a chance, as it has something to offer for readers of all ages and backgrounds.

I believe that literature is a powerful tool that can bring people from different cultures and backgrounds together. By reading works from different parts of the world, we can gain a better understanding of different perspectives and experiences. This is why I think it's important to integrate world literature with Uzbek literature.

My love for Russian literature has inspired me to become a translator when I grow up. I want to translate Uzbek literature into world languages so that more people can experience the beauty and richness of Uzbek culture. I believe that this will help to promote cultural exchange and understanding between different countries.

In order to achieve this goal, I think it's important to start by learning as much as possible about different cultures and languages. By reading works from different parts of the world, we can gain a deeper understanding of different cultures and languages. This will help us to become better translators and ambassadors of different cultures.

I have tried to translate the following work:

CITY in TABAKERK

Papa put the snuffbox on the table. "Come here, Misha, look," he said.

Misha was an obedient boy; immediately left the toys and went up to papa. Yes, it was something to see! What a lovely snuffbox! Motley, from a turtle. What's on the lid? Gates, turrets, a

house, another, third, fourth - and it is impossible to count, and everything is small, and all golden; and the trees are also golden, and the leaves on them are silver; and the sun rises behind the trees, and from it pink rays diverge throughout the sky.

- What is this town? Misha asked.

- This is the town of Tin-Din, - answered papa and touched the spring ...

And what? Suddenly, out of nowhere, music began to play. Where this music was coming from, Misha could not understand: he went to the door too - was it from another room? and to the clock—is it not on the clock? and to the bureau, and to the hill; first in one place, then in another. He also looked under the table... Finally, Misha was convinced that the music was definitely playing in the snuffbox.

- Daddy! Daddy! Is it possible to enter this town? How I wish!

- It's a trick, my friend: this town is not for your growth.

- Nothing, papa, I'm so small, just let me go there; I'd love to know what's going on there...

“Really, my friend, it’s crowded there even without you.

- But who lives there?

- Who lives there? Bells live there.

With these words, papa lifted the lid on the snuffbox, and what did he see?

Misha? And bells, and hammers, and a roller, and wheels ... Misha was surprised: “What are these bells for? Why hammers? Why a roller with hooks? Misha asked papa.

And papa answered: “I won’t tell you, Misha; look more closely and think: maybe you can guess. Just don’t touch this spring, otherwise everything will break.”

Papa went out, and Misha remained in the snuffbox. So, he sat and sat over her, looked, looked, thought, thought, why did the bells ring? Meanwhile, the music plays and plays; now everything is quieter and quieter, as if something is clinging to each note, as if something is pushing one sound away from another. Here Misha looks: a door opens at the bottom of the snuffbox, and a boy with a golden head and in a steel skirt runs out of the door, stops on the threshold and beckons Misha to him. “But why,” thought Misha, “daddy said that it’s crowded in this town even without me? No, apparently, good people live in it, you see, they invite me to visit.

- Excuse me, with the greatest joy!

With these words, Misha ran to the door and noticed with surprise that the door was exactly the same size as him. As a well-bred boy, he considered it his duty to address his guide first. “Let me know,” Misha said, “with whom do I have the honor of speaking?”

“Ding, ding, ding,” answered the stranger, “I am a bell boy, a resident of this town. We heard that you really want to visit us, and therefore we decided to ask you to do us the honor of visiting us. Ding-ding-ding, ding-ding.

Misha bowed politely; the bell-boy took him by the hand, and they went. Then Misha noticed that above them was a vault made of colorful embossed paper with golden edges. Before them was another vault, only smaller; then the third, even less; the fourth, even smaller, and so all the other arches - the farther, the smaller, so that it seemed that the head of his guide could hardly pass into the last one.

“I am very grateful to you for your invitation,” Misha told him, “but I don’t know if it will be possible for me to use it. True, here I can pass freely, but there, further, look at what low vaults you have, there I am, let me tell you frankly, there I will not even crawl through. I wonder how you pass under them. - Ding-ding-ding! the boy replied. “Let’s go, don’t worry, just follow me.”

Misha obeyed. In fact, with every step they took, the vaults seemed to rise, and our boys went everywhere freely; when they reached the last vault, then the bell boy asked Misha to look back.

Misha looked around, and what did he see? Now that first vault, under which he approached, entering the doors, seemed to him small, as if, while they were walking, the vault had lowered. Misha was very surprised.

- Why is this? he asked his guide.

“It always seems that way from afar. It is evident that you did not look at anything in the distance with attention. From a distance, everything seems small, but when you get closer it looks big. “Yes, it’s true,” answered Misha, “I still haven’t thought about it, and that’s why this is what happened to me: on the third day I wanted to draw how my mother plays the piano next to me, and my father reads a book on the other side of the room.” Only I couldn't do it. Mommy told me that daddy should be drawn small, but I thought that mommy was joking, because daddy was much larger than her; but now I see that she was telling the truth: papa should have been drawn small, because he was sitting far away. Thank you very much for your explanation. Thank you very much.

The bell boy laughed with all his might: “Ding, ding, ding, how funny! Not to be able to draw papa and mama! Ding-ding-ding, ding-ding-ding!” Misha felt annoyed that the bell boy was over so unmercifully mocked him, and he very politely said to him: “Let me ask you: why do you keep saying “ding-ding-ding” to every word?

“We have a saying like that,” answered the bell boy.

- Proverb? Misha noticed. - But papa said that it is very bad to get used to sayings.

Bell Boy bit his lips and didn't say another word.

Here were more doors in front of them; they opened, and Misha found her in the street. What a street! What a town! The pavement is paved with mother-of-pearl; the sky is motley, tortoiseshell; the golden sun walks across the sky; you beckon it, it will descend from the sky, go around your hand and rise again. And the houses are steel, polished, covered with multi-colored shells, and under each lid sits a bell boy with a golden head, in a silver skirt, and there are many, many, and all small and small less. “No, they won’t deceive me now,” Misha said. - It only seems so to me from afar, but the bells are all the same.

“But that’s not true,” answered the guide, “the bells are not the same. If everyone were the same, then we would all ring in one voice, one like the other, and you hear what songs we bring out. This is because whoever is bigger among us has a thicker voice. Don't you know that too? You see, Misha, this is a lesson for you: don't laugh at those who have a bad saying; one with a saying, but he knows more than another, and one can learn something from him.

Misha, in turn, bit his tongue.

Meanwhile, the bell boys surrounded them, tugging at Misha's dress, jingling, jumping, and running.

- You live merrily, - Misha told them, - a century would remain with you. The whole day you do nothing, you have no lessons, no teachers, and not even music all day long.

- Ding-ding-ding! the bells chimed. - We've found some fun! No, Misha, life is bad for us. True, we have no lessons, but what's the point? We should not be afraid of lessons. Our whole misfortune lies precisely in the fact that we poor people have nothing to do; we have neither books nor pictures; there is no father or mother; we have nothing to do; play and play all day long, but this, Misha, is very, very boring. Will you believe it? Good is our tortoiseshell sky, good is the golden sun and golden trees; but we, the poor, have seen enough of them, and we are very tired of all this; we are not a step out of the town, and you can imagine what it is like for a whole century, doing nothing, to sit in a snuffbox, and even in a snuffbox with music.

“Yes,” Misha answered, “you are telling the truth. This happens to me too: when, after school, you start playing with toys, it's so much fun; and when on a holiday you play and play all day long,

then by the evening it will become boring; and because of that, and for another toy, you will accept - everything is not cute. I did not understand for a long time; why, and now I understand.

- Yes, besides that, we have another problem, Misha: we have uncles.

- What kind of uncle? Misha asked.

“Uncles-hammers,” answered the bells, “how evil they are!” Every now and then they walk around the city and tap us. The larger ones, the more rarely the “knock-knock” happens, and even the little ones get hurt.

In fact, Misha saw that some gentle people on thin legs, with long noses, were walking along the street and whispering among themselves: “Knock-knock-knock! Knock-knock-knock, pick up! Touch! Knock-Knock!”. And in fact, uncleshammers incessantly on one bell, then on another bell, knock and knock. Misha even felt sorry for them. He went up to these gentle people, bowed to them very politely, and asked with good nature why they beat the poor boys without any regret. And the hammer answered him:

- Go away, don't interfere! There, in the ward and in a dressing gown, the warder lies and tells us to knock. Everything is tossing and turning. Knock-Knock! Knock-Knock!

- What is your overseer? Misha asked the bell.

- And this is Mr. Valik, - they rang out, - a kind man, he does not leave the sofa day and night; we cannot complain about it.

Misha - to the warden. He looks: he really lies on the sofa, in a dressing gown and turns from side to side, only his face is up. And on his dressing gown he has hairpins, hooks, apparently invisible; as soon as he comes across a hammer, he will first hook it with a hook, then lower it, and the hammer will knock on the bell.

As soon as Misha approached him, the warder shouted:

- Hanky panky! Who walks here? Who is wandering around here? Hanky panky! Who doesn't walk away? Who won't let me sleep? Hanky panky! Hanky panky!

“It's me,” Misha answered bravely, “I, Misha...”

- What do you need? the warder asked.

- Yes, I feel sorry for the poor bell boys, they are all so smart, so kind, such musicians, and at your order the uncles constantly tap them ...

- And what do I care, shura-muras! I'm not the biggest one here. Let the uncles hit the boys! What do I care? I am a kind overseer; I lie on the sofa and do not look after anyone. Shura-moors, shura-moors...

- Well, I learned a lot in this town! Misha said to himself. “Sometimes I still get annoyed. Why doesn't the warden take his eyes off me...” Meanwhile, Misha went further and stopped. Looks like a golden tent with a pearl fringe; at the top, a golden weather vane spins like a windmill, and under the tent lies the princess Spring and, like a snake, it will curl up, then turn around and constantly push the warder to the side. Misha was very surprised at this and said to her:

- Madam princess! Why are you pushing the warden to the side?

“Zits-zits-zits,” answered the princess. “You foolish boy, foolish boy. You look at everything, you see nothing! If I had not pushed the roller, the roller would not have turned; if the roller did not spin, then it would not cling to the hammers, the hammers would not knock; if the hammers did not knock, the bells would not ring; if the bells did not ring, and there would be no music! Zitz-zitz-zitz. Misha wanted to know if the princess was telling the truth. He bent down and pressed her finger - and what? In an instant, the spring developed with force, the roller spun violently, the hammers quickly clattered, the bells played rubbish, and suddenly the spring burst. Everything fell silent, the roller stopped, the hammers fell, the bells turned to the side, the sun hung, the houses broke ... Then Misha remembered

that papa did not order him to touch the spring, got scared and ... woke up.

- What did you see in a dream, Misha? asked papa.

Misha could not come to her senses for a long time. He looks: the same papa's room, the same snuffbox in front of him; papa and mama are sitting next to him and laughing.

"Where's the bell boy?" Where is uncle's hammer? Where is Princess Spring? Misha asked. "So, it was a dream?"

- Yes, Misha, the music lulled you to sleep, and you took a decent nap here. Tell us at least what you dreamed about!

"Yes, you see, papa," said Misha, rubbing his eyes, "I kept wanting to know why the music was playing in the snuffbox; so, I began to diligently look at her and make out what was moving in her and why she was moving; I thought and thought and began to get there, when suddenly, I see, the door to the snuffbox opened ... - Here Misha told his whole dream in order.

"Well, now I see," said papa, "that you really almost understood why the music plays in the snuffbox; but you will understand it even better when you study mechanics.

Overall, I believe that integrating world literature with Uzbek literature is an important step towards promoting cultural exchange and understanding between different countries. As a pupil, I am committed to learning as much as possible about different cultures and languages so that I can become a better translator and ambassador of different cultures.

In conclusion, I am proud to say that I am into Russian literature. It has opened up a whole new world of reading for me, and I can't wait to explore more books in this genre. I encourage everyone to give it a try and see for themselves what makes Russian literature so special.

REFERENCE:

1. Владимир Одоевский "Городок в табакерке (сказка Одоевского)"
2. Одоевский В. Ф. Сочинения князя В. Ф. Одоевского, ч. 1-3. (1844)
3. Одоевский В. Ф. Музыкально-литературное наследие. (1956)
4. Одоевский В. Ф. Повести и рассказы. (1959)
5. РУССКИЕ НОЧИ: художественная литература, 2012, Одоевский В. Ф., Директ-Медиа